

RDA Council

Minutes of Meetings 2024

DOI: RDA00128

Authors: Research Data Alliance

Published: 31 January 2025

Language: English

License: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

Citation and Download: Research Data Alliance Secretariat. (2025). *RDA Council Minutes of Meetings 2024*. Research Data Alliance. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00128>

RDA Council Meeting

20th February 2024 UTC 12:00-13:30

Meeting Chair: Jill Benn

Attendees:

1. Jill Benn
2. Juan Bicarregui
3. Françoise Genova (RAB)
4. Joyce Gosata Maphanyane
5. Jason Haga
6. Wolfram Horstmann
7. Amy Nurnberger
8. Gabriela Pino Chacon (OAB)
9. Rob Quick (TAB)
10. Lee Wilson
11. Hilary Hanahoe (RDA Foundation Secretary General)
12. Bridget Walker (RDA Foundation (notes))

Apologies: Ingrid Dillo, Claudia Medeiros, Connie Clare

[Conflict of Interest, Agenda approval and actions following meeting of 27 October 2023](#)

Discussion:

All actions complete except Risk assessment which will be taken forward with those concerned.

No conflicts of interest with the agenda items were expressed.

Reflection on loss of Sarah Jones, RDA Council member.

Thanks to Jason, Ingrid, Claudia and acknowledgement of their work and contributions over past 6 years to Council and to the Financial Subcommittee (Jason).

[Council Elections Update – Hilary Hanahoe \(on behalf of Ingrid Dillo, Nominations Committee Chair\)](#)

Discussion:

Council was provided with an update on the Nominations Committee and progress for the 2024 elections. 4 nominations received for 3 open seats – 2 EU & Africa, 1 US, 1 Asia & Oceania.

Candidate statements approved by the Committee having checked eligibility.

Recommendations from Committee members:

- Investigate better alignment between search activities for potential nominees by Secretary General and Committee members.

- Explore possibility to move nomination process ahead in time to allow for better timing in southern hemisphere.
- Reiterate recommendation from 2023 Nominations Committee that disciplinary balancing criteria could be removed due to not being meaningful or feasible for RDA Council.

Decision:

Nominations Committee Terms of Reference to be updated with Committee recommendations.

[RDA Technical Advisory Board Update – Rob Quick](#)

Discussion:

Council was presented with an update on TAB activities including the issue of inactive members and action required.

Decision:

Document on definition of active/inactive TAB members to be drawn up by TAB with Secretariat support.

[RDA Foundation Financial Update – Juan Bicarregui](#)

Discussion:

Council was provided with an update on the RDA Foundation's financial status first quarter 2024 and forecast for the year 2024.

[RDA Strategy 2024-2028 and Implementation Plan \(January 2024-June 2025\) – Hilary Hanahoe](#)

Discussion:

Council was presented with the implementation actions for each strategic area and priorities for the period January 2024 to June 2025. Members discussed involving others board and regional members to support the plan.

Decision:

Council approved the implementation plan and the flexibility with the need to prioritise business as usual and then balance the actions across the 4 strategic pillars. A call to action was also approved to engage board members and/or stakeholder groups.

[Web Platform Update – Hilary Hanahoe](#)

Discussion:

Council was presented with an update on the progress of the new web platform and timing for launch, scheduled for 25 March 2024.

Acknowledgement to staff in Canada and EU office for assistance in content migration.

[Council Meetings Calendar – Lee Wilson](#)

Discussion:

Council was presented with a proposed meeting calendar matrix to better map out agenda items and high level strategic priorities and give clarity on Council meeting types required throughout the year.

Decision:

Council members approved the proposed calendar matrix and tasked Hilary Hanahoe with incorporating lead times and preparatory actions for agenda items.

AOB

Remembering Sarah Jones

Council discussed the several proposed initiatives from different RDA members and external people. The RDA would like to establish an award for an RDA community member, recognising contribution to open science and the community.

Coordination of award to be discussed by Hilary, Gabriela, Juan, Jill, Rob and Kevin Ashley (DCC).

OAB Update

OAB provided Council with a written update prior to the meeting.

Next Council Meetings

Council agreed the next conference call would take place mid to late April followed by a face to face meeting in Prague 14 June 2024, on the occasion of PIDfest.

RDA Council Meeting 30 April 2024 UTC 11:00-12:30

Meeting Chair: Lee Wilson

Attendees:

1. Jill Benn
2. Juan Bicarregui
3. Raphael Cobe (TAB)
4. Maria Cruz
5. Françoise Genova (RAB)
6. Joyce Gosata Maphanyane
7. Wolfram Horstmann
8. Amy Nurnberger
9. Rob Quick (TAB)
10. Shelley Stall (OAB)
11. Mikiko Tanifuji
12. Lee Wilson
13. Hilary Hanahoe (RDA Foundation Secretary General)
14. Connie Clare (RDA Foundation)
15. Bridget Walker (RDA Foundation (notes))

Apologies: Patricia Munoz Palma

[Conflict of Interest, Agenda approval and actions following meeting of 20 February 2024](#)

Discussion:

All actions complete except the following to be carried over:

- Active/inactive TAB member document.
- Call for Involvement of different stakeholder engagement – RDA Strategy Implementation Plan

No conflicts of interest with the agenda items were expressed.

[Welcome to New Council Members](#)

Maria Cruz and Mikiko Tanifuji welcomed and introduced to the Council and attending Secretariat members. The other new Council member, Patricia Munoz Palma, was not in attendance and sent her apologies.

[RDA Foundation Financial Update – Juan Bicarregui](#)

Discussion:

Hilary Hanahoe provided an overview on how the RDA is funded for the benefit of new Council members,
Juan Bicarregui, Financial Subcommittee Chair highlighted the RDA Foundation's financial status for the first quarter 2024, and forecasts for 2024 and 2025-2028 following distribution of the written financial summary distributed to Council prior to the meeting.

Decision:

As a result of discussions, it was decided Hilary Hanahoe would continue discussions with the Research Software Alliance to collaborate on financially supporting a person in Latin America to raise awareness of Open Science leveraging on SCOSS funds paid to date.

[Regional Advisory Board – Francoise Genova](#)

Discussion:

Council was provided with an update on activities of the Regional Advisory Board and Regional Assembly by co-chair Francoise Genova. This included a summary of the RDA Around the World regional webinars and the P22 regional plenary sessions proposals.

Decision:

Extension of Francoise Genova's co-chair role to be discussed at Council meeting in June. Francoise Genova and Wolfram Horstman to discuss the Europe status and P22 plenary session with Alex Delipalta, Director of Operations of the RDA EU Association (AISBL).

[RDA New Web Platform – Hilary Hanahoe](#)

Discussion:

Council was presented with an update on the status of the new web platform launch and its functionalities.

[RDA 22nd Plenary Meeting – Irina Hope / Hilary Hanahoe](#)

Discussion:

Irina Hope, RDA Global Events Manager, and Hilary Hanahoe presented Council with an update on RDA P22 taking place 14-23 May 2024 as a fully virtual event. This covered registration, sessions overview and the newly proposed Equality and Diversity Programme for Plenaries (EDPP) to be piloted at P22. Alignment with the RDA Strategy Plan 2024-2028 was highlighted.

Decision:

Council requested that insights into P22 be given at the next Council meeting 14th June 2024.

[Council Face to Face Meeting 14 June 2024 – Jill Benn / Lee Wilson](#)

Discussion:

Council Co-chairs proposed agenda items to be included in the next Council meeting, taking place after PIDfest 2024 in Prague on 14 June 2024.

Decision:

Council approved the proposed agenda items with the addition of a short item on an analysis of RDA plenaries to be followed by a discussion on the future of International Data Week.

AOB

OAB and TAB Updates

Written updates were provided to Council prior to the meeting.

RDA Council Meeting
14 June 2024 UTC 07:00-13:00
National Library of Technology, Prague

Meeting Chair: Lee Wilson

Attendees:

1. Juan Bicarregui
2. Maria Cruz
3. Joyce Gosata Maphanyane - virtual
4. Rosie Hicks
5. Amy Nurnberger - virtual
6. Rob Quick (TAB) - virtual
7. Shelley Stall (OAB) - virtual
8. Mikiko Tanifuji - virtual
9. Lee Wilson
10. Hilary Hanahoe (RDA Foundation Secretary General)
11. Irina Hope (RDA Foundation)
12. Connie Clare (RDA Foundation) - virtual
13. Bridget Walker (RDA Foundation (notes))

Apologies: Jill Benn, Wolfram Horstmann, Patricia Munoz Palma

Executive Committee Meeting 07:00-07:30 UTC

Elected RDA Council members and STFC representative, Juan Bicarregui discussed:

- Request from RAB co-chairs to extend Francoise Genova's role for one year - approved.
- Consideration of nomination of Sara Garavelli as European Council member to take up vacant European seat (2024-2026) with the possibility of running for a 2nd term in 2026 – approval for Hilary Hanahoe to move forward with formal invitation. RDA Governance Document to be updated with Council given the decision on replacing lost Council members.
- Additional member to the Financial Subcommittee – decision for Hilary Hanahoe to put a request in writing to Council.
- Extension of Jill Benn's role as Council Co-chair by one year – approved.
- Secretary General annual appraisal – Council Co-chairs to proceed and inform Council.

[Conflict of Interest, Agenda approval and actions following meeting of 20 February 2024](#)

Discussion:

All actions complete except the following to be carried over:

- Active/inactive TAB member document.
- RDA Strategy Implementation Plan

No conflicts of interest with the agenda items were expressed.

[RDA Web Platform Delay and Budgetary Issues – Hilary Hanahoe](#)

Discussion:

Due to the RDA web platform being significantly delayed and issues with the developers, including possible additional costs, Hilary Hanahoe updated Council on the current situation. This was followed by a discussion on the next steps in terms of scenarios and budgets.

Decision:

As a result of the discussions, it was decided Hilary Hanahoe would check the contract with Wicket, the web developers and she would also contact the Wicket CEO immediately to confirm the meeting scheduled for 21st June with herself and Lee Wilson. An emergency Council meeting was scheduled for the week beginning 24th June.

[Organisational Assembly / Organisational Advisory Board – Shelley Stall](#)

Agenda item postponed due to lengthy website and then IDW discussions, and Co-chair Shelley Stall's need to leave the meeting early. Shelley Stall to send a written report to Council.

[RDA Plenaries Analysis and Future Editions of IDW – Irina Hope](#)

Discussion:

Council was presented with an overview of the plenary analysis carried out by Irina Hope with the aim of confirming or adjusting the RDA Plenary Policy of two plenary meetings per year, one of which fully virtual and the other hybrid. The future of RDA plenaries in the framework of International Data Week (IDW) was also discussed.

Decision:

Council approved the continuation of RDA fully virtual plenary meetings and hybrid plenary meetings, the latter not having co-located events organised by RDA Secretariat. From P24 virtual plenary meetings will take place over one week instead of two and repeat sessions should be removed from virtual plenary meetings. Council confirmed its preference to continue with IDW but gave the mandate to continue past 2027 which should involve proposal of a new model within the same framework.

[RDA Risk Registry – Task Force](#)

Discussion:

Juan Bicarregui gave an overview of the task force's progress to date with the risk assessment, explaining the risks and issues considered and included in the draft template.

Decision:

The task force will follow up by email to Council requesting feedback on the Risk Assessment spreadsheet and framework. The task force will meet again with an extension to TAB co-chairs to join to discuss engagement with other governing bodies.

[Sarah Jones Award – Hilary Hanahoe](#)

Discussion:

An update on the status of the Sarah Jones Award was given, followed by a discussion on the Award selection committee.

Decision:

Council gave approval for Hilary Hanahoe to invite members to form a selection committee.

[RDA In Latin America – Hilary Hanahoe](#)

Discussion:

Council was presented with a summary of Hilary Hanahoe's recent tour of Latin America which involved visiting 9 countries, facilitated by LA Referencia and funded by the RDA. The overarching takeaways were highlighted which included the provision of training materials on the RDA, RDM and FAIR to help support the culture change, and facilitation of content translation and interpretation at plenary meetings.

[Update on Regional Support – Hilary Hanahoe](#)

Discussion:

An update on regional support to the RDA with particular focus on prospects for the US and EU was provided, followed by a discussion on regional engagement partnerships with Europe and the US and the impact on RDA Global from 2025 onwards. It was highlighted that only one of the three major founding funders of the RDA is in a stable situation.

Decision:

Council approved the proposal for a combined meeting with the RDA Foundation Council members and RDA Association (AISBL) Board members prior to RDA P23 in Costa Rica, November 2024.

[AOB](#)

No topics were raised.

RDA Council Meeting

5 September 2024 UTC 12:00-13:30

Meeting Chair: Lee Wilson

Attendees:

1. Juan Bicarregui
2. Sara Garavelli
3. Francoise Genova (RA/B)
4. Wolfram Horstmann
5. Amy Nurnberger
6. Gabriela Pino Chacon (OA/B)
7. Lee Wilson
8. Hilary Hanahoe (RDA Foundation Secretary General)
9. Bridget Walker (RDA Foundation (notes))

Apologies: Jill Benn, Maria Cruz, Joyce Gosata Maphanyane, Patricia Munoz Palma, Rob Quick (TAB), Mikiko Tanifuji

[Conflict of Interest, Agenda approval and actions following meeting of 14 June 2024](#)

Discussion:

All actions complete except the following to be carried over:

- Active/inactive TAB member document.
- Call for Involvement of different stakeholder engagement – RDA Strategy Implementation Plan
- Governance document to be updated with decision on replacement of lost Council member.
- Financial subcommittee additional member.

No conflicts of interest with the agenda items were expressed.

[Welcome to New Council Member](#)

Sara Garavelli, filling the vacant Council seat, welcomed and introduced to the Council and attending Secretariat members.

[RDA Foundation Financial Status Update – Hilary Hanahoe](#)

Discussion:

Hilary Hanahoe provided an update on the current financial situation and forecast 2024-2028, following distribution of the written financial summary distributed to Council prior to the meeting, including the impact of broken commitments and unforeseen expenses for the new web platform.

Regional engagement and financial contributions were discussed followed by the need for setting up a Financial Sustainability Taskforce to look into potential funding sources and activities.

Decision:

As a result of discussions, it was decided Wolfram Horstmann, Juan Bicarregui and Sara Garavelli, with the support of Hilary Hanahoe, would form the new Financial Sustainability Taskforce.

[Web Update – Hilary Hanahoe](#)

Discussion:

Council was provided with an update on the situation with the new web platform, with an explanation of the considerable inadequacy of the work performed by the Canadian based developers.

[AOB](#)

[Face to Face Council Meeting 11 Nov 2024 Agenda](#)

Council agreed to the proposed agenda and structure with some modifications.

[Additional Council Member for Financial Subcommittee](#)

Due to lack of time, it was agreed this would be decided via email.

RDA Council Meeting
San Jose, Costa Rica (RDA P23)
11 November 2024 UTC 15:00-21:30, local 09:00-15:30

Meeting Chairs: Lee Wilson & Juan Bicarregui

Attendees:

1. Juan Bicarregui
2. Sara Garavelli
3. Rosie Hicks (RA/B)
4. Wolfram Horstmann
5. Patricia Munoz Palma
6. Amy Nurnberger
7. Gabriela Pino Chacon (OA/B)
8. Shelley Stall (OA/B)
9. Mikiko Tanifuji
10. Lee Wilson
11. Hilary Hanahoe (RDA Foundation Secretary General)
12. Bridget Walker (RDA Foundation (notes))

Apologies: Jill Benn, Maria Cruz, Joyce Gosata Maphanyane

RDA AISBL:

1. Alexandra Delipalta, Director
2. Sandra Collins, Trustee
3. Ingrid Dillo, Trustee
4. Edit Herczog, Trustee

RDA US:

1. Beth Plale, Director

[Conflict of Interest, Agenda approval and actions following meeting of 5 Sept 2024](#)

Discussion:

All actions complete except the following to be carried over:

- Active/inactive TAB member document – format of document to be revisited.
- Governance document revision with inclusion of provision for loss of Council members.

No conflicts of interest with the agenda items were expressed.

[RDA in Europe Update – Alex Delipalta](#)

Discussion:

Alexandra Delipalta was invited to give a presentation to Council on the existing strengths, opportunities, weaknesses and threats of RDA in Europe following a previously circulated briefing paper to all attendees. Council discussed EU regional engagement prospects and challenges with the Director and the RDA AISBL Trustees.

[RDA in US Update – Beth Plale](#)

Discussion:

Beth Plale was invited to give a presentation to Council on the existing strengths, opportunities, weaknesses and threats of RDA in US was presented to Council by Beth Plale, following a previously circulated briefing paper to all attendees. Council discussed US regional engagement prospects and challenges with the US Director.

[Status of Regional Engagement – Hilary Hanahoe](#)

Discussion:

Regional engagement risks and opportunities were presented to Council following circulation of a briefing paper to all attendees. Discussion topics included financial sustainability, grant funding, organisational membership and plenaries.

[The Future of the RDA and RDA EU Legal Entity](#)

(attended by RDA Council members only)

Discussion:

Council members discussed all points raised during the presentations from the RDA EU and RDA US representatives, considering the challenges and solutions.

Decision:

Council set up subgroups to assess and revise the RDA Global financial sustainability strategy (previous work concluded in 2022).